

ON THE EVALUATION OF G_{12} IN THE OFF-AXIS TENSION TEST

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ABSTRACT

The apparent value of G_{12} obtained using the off-axis tension test may lead to wrong results for certain combinations of fiber orientation and geometrical aspect ratio of the specimen. Different approaches have been proposed to solve this problem, one of them having been used in this paper to correct the experimental results obtained from the tests. The apparent values of G_{12} are modified by the application of a correction factor obtained from a parametric numerical analysis. The validity of the boundary conditions assumed and the repeatability of the experimental results are finally discussed.

Keywords: Graphite-epoxy, Off-Axis test, Intralaminar Shear modulus, Numerical analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most widely used test methods in the evaluation of the intralaminar shear modulus G_{12} is the off-axis tension test. However, it is well known that accurate results can only be found when the fiber orientation angle is greater than 30-deg and/or the aspect ratio (length/width) is larger than 10.

In the usual case where the specimen geometry does not satisfy the above requirements, it would be necessary to use one of the approaches proposed by several researchers for the improvement of G_{12} values. There are two general ways to do this. One of them involves the modification of the specimen configuration in order to obtain the uniform state of stress in the test section associated to the ideal (simply supported) support conditions, and the second approach type consists in the application of a correction factor over the apparent values provided by the experimental measurement.

In the first approach Sun and Berreth [1] developed a new end tab design trying to eliminate constraint effects on the specimen. In the second, Pindera and Herakovich [2] proposed a correction factor based on an analytical model by Pagano and Halpin [3], and using a special grip system which allows rotations at the end of the specimen.

Cañas, Paris and Marín [4] discussed the results obtained with this second approach and proposed a correction method based on the numerical solution of the problem assuming clamped ends, which at first sight would be the boundary conditions expected for most of the testing machines. The approach, which will be summarized in section 2, was based on a parametric numerical analysis of the clamped specimen. This method could cover the above mentioned range of fiber orientation angle and geometrical aspect ratio where the direct results are not correct, so that it would make it possible

to obtain accurate values of G_{12} by means of a simple off-axis tension test with no special fixtures for any situation.

The objective of this paper is to check by means of experimental research the accuracy of the results provided by the application of the correction factor proposed in [4].

2. THE APPROACH TO CORRECT G_{12}

In an off-axis tension test the direct experimental measures permit the calculation of the G_{12} apparent value (G_{12}^*), which is defined as:

$$G_{12}^* = \frac{\tau_{12}^*}{\gamma_{12}} \quad ; \quad \tau_{12}^* = -\bar{\sigma}_x \sin\theta \cos\theta \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_x$ is the average longitudinal stress, θ is the fiber orientation angle, and γ_{12} is the shear strain.

The proposed correction method for G_{12}^* [4], obtained from an off-axis tension test, is based on the numerical solution of the problem assuming clamped ends. The test will consequently have to be developed trying to reproduce these conditions. The numerical solution was found by means of a finite elements analysis carried out for a wide range of geometrical configurations and mechanical properties. A certain number of correctors graphs representing the relation between the correct and the apparent value of G_{12} versus the ratio between the shear strain γ_{12} and the longitudinal strain ϵ_x in the central point of the specimen were obtained as a result of this numerical study. Figure 1 shows one of them for a certain value of the aspect ratio.

Figure 1.- Corrector graph for ratio=10, and for different fiber orientation angle.

The mechanical properties of the material are not involved because a parametric study showed [4] the almost independence, with regard to the properties E_{11} , E_{22} , ν_{12} , of the quotient between the apparent value of G_{12} and its correct value. This fact, not initially apparent, allows a great

simplification of the developed approach from the point view of its application. In this way the graphs make it possible to find, for each configuration (aspect ratio and fiber orientation angle), the value of correction factor that must be applied to the apparent value of G_{12}^* in order to find the correct value G_{12} . For this purpose one may enter into the graph with the experimental values γ_{12}/ϵ_x and determine the intersection with the corresponding line, as shown in Figure 1. The values of γ_{12} and ϵ_x would be obtained from a strain gauge rosette placed at the center of the specimen.

3. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

An experimental study has been carried out to investigate the accuracy of the proposed method. The material employed is a unidirectional laminate made of graphite-epoxy, designated AS-4/3501-6 and manufactured by HTC.

As a first step, the material was characterized determining E_{11} , E_{22} and ν_{12} , in order to verify whether the values lay within the range of validity of the graphs generated and also to allow numerical analysis to simulate the tests. The tests were carried out according to the ASTM D-3039, obtaining the following results:

$$E_{11}= 151.5 \text{ GPa} ; E_{22}= 13.67 \text{ GPa} ; \nu_{12}= 0.343$$

In a second phase, three series of 30-deg and 10-deg Off-Axis specimens were tested under three different aspect ratios ($L/h= 6,8$ and 10). The specimen geometry configuration is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2.- Specimen geometry configuration.

The reason for including the 30-deg specimens was the direct determination, without the application of any correction factor, of a sufficiently approximate value of G_{12} , because the slight influence of end constraints for specimens with fiber orientation angle equal to or greater than 30 degrees is well known [2,4].

The objective of the research carried out was to investigate the behaviour of reasonably short specimens because it is known that no correction factors are required for long, but not practical, specimens. Less than 10 aspect ratios were then considered, 6 being the lowest figure allowing the instrumentation of specimens and also due to some fixture limitations.

The specimens were instrumented with a Micromeritics WK-06-060WR-350 strain gauge rosette to determine γ_{12} and ϵ_x at the central point. The value of τ_{12}^* is obtained by applying (1), once the average value of the longitudinal stress is obtained dividing the applied load (provided by the test machine) by the nominal area of the specimen. The tests were performed on an Instron machine using a grip system - Figure 3 - which generates a lateral load on the specimen that increases with its elongation. No end tabs were used in these tests, although sandpaper was employed between the jaws and the specimen so that the probability of sliding was reduced.

Figure 3.- Gripping system scheme.

From the results of 30-deg tests shown in Figure 4, close agreement between all the graphs (only those corresponding to the extreme aspect ratios 6 and 10 have been represented in the Figure), which represent τ_{12}^* versus γ_{12} , was observed. This was expected from the results of previous research [2, 4].

A value of $G_{12}=5.5$ GPa was assumed as the correct value of the material, taken from the slope of the experimental behaviour. Using this value, a numerical analysis was performed modelling the grip action as simple supported and clamped end conditions. The results, also shown in Figure 4, present, as was expected, a reasonable agreement with each other and also with respect to the experimental ones.

Figure 4.- Experimental and numerical results for 30-deg off-axis test.

Taking again the value of G_{12} from the 30-deg test as input data for the numerical analysis of the 10-deg Off-Axis problem, the graphs τ_{12}^* vs. γ_{12} represented in Figure 5 were obtained. The analysis was again performed for the same two boundary conditions used in the 30-deg case, and for three different aspect ratios ($L/h = 6, 8$ and 10). These two boundary conditions are considered because it is believed that they represent extreme conditions, any real situation lying somewhere between

them. The numerical results show an expected increment of the apparent intralaminar shear modulus with the boundary conditions (simply supported to clamped end) and with the decrease in the aspect ratio.

Figure 5.- Numerical 10-deg off-axis values for several conditions.

The following Figures 6, 7 and 8 show the experimental results obtained for the three aspect ratios under consideration. The previously mentioned numerical results, appropriate to each case, are included, to be taken as a reference.

Figure 6.- Experimental and numerical 10-deg results for aspect ratio 6.

Figure 7.- Experimental and numerical 10-deg results for aspect ratio 8.

Figure 8.- Experimental and numerical 10-deg results for aspect ratio 10.

First of all, it has to be pointed out that although the same gripping system was used for all the specimens tested the results present, particularly for the cases of aspect ratios equal to 8 and 10, a clear lack of uniformity, not specifically in accordance with the numerical results associated to the assumption of clamped end condition. The case of aspect ratio equal to 6 presents only two results because of damage to one of the specimens in preparing the test. The two results obtained almost fit the expected numerical behaviour associated to clamped end conditions. The other two cases present an intermediate behaviour between the two numerical conditions analyzed, such behaviour being

attributable to some relative sliding between the gripping surfaces which generates an indeterminate partial clamped condition.

The experimental results obtained would appear to question the proposed approach to correct the apparent value of G_{12} because some of the tests (those showing a close comparison with the simply supported case), lead without any modification to an apparent value of G_{12} which is almost identical to the true value. However, a certain checking of the approach, which is based on the assumption that clamped end conditions hold, can be performed taking into consideration only the results for which it is reasonable to accept that these boundary conditions have occurred. It is possible, for these cases, to apply the appropriate correction factor over the apparent value G_{12}^* calculated as the slope of the τ_{12}^* vs. γ_{12} curve. The results of such a procedure are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental and corrected values of G_{12} .

L/h	γ_{12}/ϵ_x	G_{12}/G_{12}^*	G_{12}^* (GPa)	Error in apparent value (%)	G_{12}^c (GPa)	Error in corrected value (%)
6	1.94	0.708	7.594	38.07	5.37	2.36
10	2.24	0.874	6.35	15.45	5.55	0.9

The application of the correction factor (whose determination is shown in Figure 1 for the case of aspect ratio equal to 10) on G_{12} produces corrected values G_{12}^c with a significant error reduction.

4. CONCLUSIONS

As the above results show, the suitability of the proposed approach, when the specimen behaviour is like a clamped end off-axis test, is proved even for low aspect ratio. However, it is not possible, from the different types of behaviour found, to assure the equivalence between the actual conditions generated by the gripping system and the modelled boundary conditions (clamped ends) for the numerical correction factor evaluation.

The lack of repeatability from the number of tests performed cannot support any definitive conclusion from a practical point of view. It seems that if rotations were allowed absolutely at the ends (a situation found in some tests) a correction factor would not be required. It also seems that if rotations are not allowed the proposed approach works very well. The problem is obviously knowing what the actual behaviour will be in a real test.

The problem seems a very complicated one to solve and two directions of research should be followed, in the opinion of the authors, in order to reach a better knowledge of the problem. One would be a parametric study of the errors induced in the results by some factors of uncertainty inherent to the test (misalignment of the specimen with the load, small variations of the nominal fiber angle orientation, etc.). The other would be a more detailed experimental analysis of the gauge length or, even better, close to the grip, probably using a moiré technique, to have more information in order to give an explanation of the effects of the grip system. If it is to be of general application, the study should be extended to different grip systems.

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